

RELATIONSHIP OF NOMOPHOBIA WITH ANXIETY AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Nomophobia or the fear of not having a mobile phone has become an increasing psychological health problem among university students in the digital era.

Purpose: To analyze the correlation between nomophobia, anxiety and quality of life in undergraduate students.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 282 undergraduate students from nursing, physiotherapy, and pharmacy programs at LUMHS, Jamshoro. Data collection instruments included the Nomophobia Questionnaire (NMP-Q), Beck's Anxiety Inventory (BAI), and WHOQOL-BREF. Data were analyzed using SPSS v26 with chi-square tests and multinomial logistic regression. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 88.7% of students reported some degree of nomophobia: 34% mild, 39.3% moderate, and 15.2% severe. Nomophobia was significantly associated with anxiety ($p < 0.001$), with female students reporting higher levels of both nomophobia and anxiety compared to males. Quality of life domains, particularly psychological and social well-being, were negatively affected.

Conclusion: The condition of nomophobia is very widespread among students in undergraduate universities and is closely associated with anxiety and lower quality of life. There is need to employ preventive measures, sensitization and counseling interventions to reduce its impacts.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the widespread adoption of mobile phones has transformed the way individuals communicate, study, and interact socially. Alongside the benefits of constant connectivity, a new behavioral phenomenon known as nomophobia, or “no-mobile-phone

phobia,” has emerged. It is characterized by feelings of anxiety, distress, or discomfort when individuals are unable to access or use their mobile phones (Humood et al., 2021).

Nomophobia is increasingly recognized as a psychological and behavioral health concern,

particularly among young adults and university students. Studies have linked it to poor academic performance, sleep disturbances, reduced social interaction, and heightened levels of anxiety and depression (Abdoli et al., 2023; Sharma, Mathur, & Jeenger, 2019). Female students, in particular, appear to be more vulnerable, with higher reported rates of smartphone dependence and nomophobia compared to males (Janatolmakan, Karampour, Rezaeian, & Khatony, 2024).

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the level of nomophobia among undergraduate students.
- To examine the relationship of nomophobia and anxiety.
- To evaluate the impact of nomophobia on quality of life domains

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of nomophobia originated in 2008 in the UK and has since gained international attention as a modern digital-age anxiety disorder (Sharma et al., 2019). Global prevalence studies show rates varying between 15% and 99%, depending on the measurement tools and study populations (Humood et al., 2021). University students, particularly those in health-related disciplines, are among the most affected groups (Saleem, Shahzad, Husnain, & Asad, 2022).

Nomophobia is strongly correlated with anxiety. Research has demonstrated that students with higher nomophobia scores report greater social anxiety, poorer sleep quality, and reduced academic performance (Fatima, Fatima, Taufiq, Fiaz, & Afzal, 2024). In addition, nomophobia has been found to negatively influence multiple domains of quality of life, including psychological well-being, social relationships, and physical health (Demircioğlu & Genç, 2024; Gonçalves, Dias, & Correia, 2020).

Treatment approaches include cognitive-behavioral therapy, counseling, and structured interventions such as digital detox programs and physical activity promotion (Farchakh et al., 2021). Preventive strategies, including awareness campaigns and digital well-being education, have

also been recommended (Bernabé-Mateo, Onieva-Zafra, Muñoz-Rodríguez, Bermejo-Cantarero, & Romero-Blanco, 2025; Notara, Vagka, Gnardellis, & Lagiou, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, Pakistan, including the People's Nursing School, College of Pharmacy & Therapeutics, and College of Physiotherapy & Rehabilitation Sciences. The study population comprised undergraduate students (BS Nursing, Doctor of Pharmacy, and Doctor of Physiotherapy), and a sample size of 282 was determined using OpenEpi with a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence level, and a prevalence estimate of 57.6% (Fatima et al., 2024), selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using standardized tools: The Nomophobia Questionnaire (NMP-Q; 20 items, Cronbach's $\alpha=0.92$, score categories: no nomophobia=20, mild=21-59, moderate=60-99, severe=100-140), Beck's Anxiety Inventory (BAI; 21 items, score categories: 0-21=mild, 22-35=moderate, ≥ 36 =severe), and the WHOQOL-BREF (26 items assessing physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains, Cronbach's $\alpha=0.93$). Questionnaires were distributed face-to-face after obtaining informed consent. Data were analyzed in SPSS v26 using descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentages) for demographic variables, chi-square tests for associations, and multinomial logistic regression to identify predictors of quality of life, with a significance level set at $p<0.05$.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical considerations for this study include:

- The study received ethical approval from the Ethical Review Committee of Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro.
- Informed consent taken in written format from participants after explaining to them about the study.
- The identity and confidentiality of participant's information kept private

throughout the data collection, analysis, and interpretation process.

- ERC and LUMHS standard research protocols were followed in the entire study.

RESULTS

Table No. 01: Demographic characteristics of participants (N=282)

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	84	29.8
	Female	198	70.2
Age (years)	Mean ± SD	22.1 ± 3.3	-
Marital Status	Unmarried	271	96.1
	Married	11	3.9
Discipline	Nursing	76	26.9
	Pharmacy	93	32.9
	Physiotherapy	113	40.0

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the study participants (N=282). The majority of the respondents were female (70.2%), while males accounted for 29.8%. The mean age of participants was 22.1 years (SD ± 3.3), indicating that most belonged to the young adult group. In terms of marital status, an overwhelming majority

were unmarried (96.1%), with only 3.9% being married. Regarding academic disciplines, 26.9% of students were enrolled in Nursing, 32.9% in Pharmacy, and 40.0% in Physiotherapy, reflecting a diverse representation of undergraduate programs.

Table No. 02: Levels of Nomophobia among participants

Level of Nomophobia	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
No Nomophobia	32	11.3
Mild	96	34.0
Moderate	111	39.3
Severe	43	15.2

Table 2 shows the distribution of nomophobia levels among the participants. The findings reveal that the majority of students experienced moderate levels of nomophobia (39.3%), followed by mild levels (34.0%). Severe nomophobia was reported by 15.2% of

participants, while only 11.3% reported no nomophobia. These results indicate that a substantial proportion of undergraduate student's experience mild to moderate nomophobia, with a notable proportion also affected by severe levels.

Table No. 03: Levels of Anxiety among participants

Level of Anxiety	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mild	101	35.8
Moderate	127	45.0
Severe	54	19.1

Table 3 presents the levels of anxiety among the participants. The majority of students reported moderate anxiety (45.0%), followed by mild

anxiety in 35.8% of participants. Severe anxiety was observed in 19.1% of students. These findings highlight that more than half of the

undergraduate students experienced moderate to severe levels of anxiety, indicating a considerable

prevalence of psychological distress within the study population.

Table No. 04: Associations between Nomophobia, Anxiety, and Quality of Life

Variable	χ^2 / OR	p-value	Notes
Nomophobia vs. Anxiety	$\chi^2=57.5$	<0.001	Strong positive association
Nomophobia vs. Psychological QoL	OR=3.3	<0.05	Significant negative impact
Nomophobia vs. Social Relationships	OR=8.1	0.02	Highly significant negative impact

Table 4 illustrates the associations between nomophobia, anxiety, and quality of life among the participants. A strong positive association was observed between nomophobia and anxiety ($\chi^2=57.5$, $p<0.001$), indicating that higher levels of nomophobia were significantly related to increased anxiety. Furthermore, nomophobia showed a significant negative impact on the psychological domain of quality of life (OR=3.3, $p<0.05$) and an even stronger negative impact on social relationships (OR=8.1, $p=0.02$). These results suggest that nomophobia not only elevates anxiety levels but also adversely affects both psychological well-being and social interactions of undergraduate students.

DISCUSSION

This study highlights the high prevalence of nomophobia among undergraduate students in Pakistan, consistent with global evidence. Approximately 89% of participants reported some degree of nomophobia, with nearly 40% experiencing moderate levels. These findings align with research conducted in Saudi Arabia and India, which similarly reported high prevalence among university populations (Alkalash et al., 2023; Thomas, Ramesh, Kumar, & Chellaiyan, 2024).

The significant association between nomophobia and anxiety reinforces existing literature suggesting that smartphone dependence contributes to psychological distress (Sharma et al., 2019). Female students in our study reported higher nomophobia and anxiety levels, consistent with studies from Egypt and Pakistan that

identified gender differences in digital dependence (Janatolmakan et al., 2024; Schwaiger & Tahir, 2020). Cultural and social factors, such as communication patterns and gender-based expectations, may explain these differences.

Quality of life domains, particularly psychological well-being and social relationships, were negatively affected by nomophobia. This mirrors findings from (Demircioğlu & Genç, 2024; Gonçalves et al., 2020), who linked nomophobia with sleep disturbances, reduced physical activity, and poor psychological outcomes. Our findings suggest that interventions to address nomophobia should prioritize not only individual counseling but also institutional awareness campaigns and digital well-being programs.

The implications of this study extend to university administrations and policymakers. Integrating digital health literacy into curricula and promoting healthier digital habits could mitigate the adverse effects of nomophobia on academic and psychological outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Nomophobia is highly prevalent among undergraduate students in Pakistan and significantly associated with increased anxiety and reduced quality of life. Female students were disproportionately affected. The study underscores the urgency of developing preventive strategies, such as awareness campaigns, counseling services, and digital well-being education, within university settings.

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